

Higher Education Management Policy in the Promotion of Lecturers' Functional Positions: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT: *One of the lecturers' obligations is to carry out career development in the promotion of functional positions. This promotion can affect the performance of the institution and the quality of teaching resources. However, there are still 426 lecturers at Politeknik Negeri Bandung (Polban) who have not performed these obligations periodically and even there are still 230 lecturers who do not propose functional position promotion for more than 10 years. This study aims to describe the lecturers' understanding of the promotion of functional positions and describe the management policy of Polban in supporting the promotion of functional positions. This study used the qualitative descriptive method. Data collection related to the knowledge and understanding of lecturers about the promotion of functional positions was collected through questionnaires distributed to lecturers who already have functional positions in Polban. The results showed that lecturers have a good understanding of the obligation to perform functional promotion and the management of Polban has provided support to lecturers with the launch of the Credit Score Assessment Information System which facilitates lecturers to conduct scientific paper assessments and propose functional position promotion online.*

KEYWORDS –functional positions, lecturers, policy, Polban

I. INTRODUCTION

High commitment from the management of higher education in controlling human resources, especially lecturers will determine the success of the education process. One of the lecturer management activities is to encourage lecturers to carry out their duties for the satisfaction of students and graduate users, as accountability to the community. Related to this, every lecturer must understand and be able to identify their duties and responsibilities.

Law Number 14 the Year 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers in article 1 verse 2 states that lecturers are professional educators and scientists with the main task of transforming, developing, and disseminating science, technology, and art through education, research, and community service. In line with this law, the Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform Number 17 the Year 2013 concerning Lecturer Functional Positions and Credit Scores in article 4 states that the main tasks of lecturers are to carry out education, research, and community service. This main task is also known as Tri Dharma Perguruan Tinggi or the Three Pillars of Higher Education.

Based on the three pillars of higher education, lecturers are not only good at delivering lectures but are also required to be professional in conducting research and community service. Since they have a strategic position in determining the quality of graduates and institution in general, higher education management is obliged to provide assistance and development to lecturers to improve the quality of educational resources (Khairuddin, 2019). Efforts to develop and improve the performance and career development of lecturers are an endless need because these efforts are not only carried out when a gap between the actual performance and the

expected performance exists, but these should also be conducted constantly. This is because the changes in the external environment of higher education are rapid which will lead to higher demands for higher education, in agreement with the needs of industries or stakeholders.

The lecturer's functional position is a position that shows the duties, responsibilities, authorities, and rights of a lecturer in a higher education unit which in its implementation is based on certain expertise. It indicates the positions of lecturers' expertise from the lowest to the highest levels; Instructor, Assistant Professor, Associate Professor, and Professors (Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform No. 17 the Year 2013 concerning Functional Positions of Lecturers and Credit Scores, Article 6 verse 2). Further, the level of lecturers' functional positions is determined by the number of credit points owned by the lecturer after being legalized by the authorized officers/assessors to determine the credit score (Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform Number 17 the Year 2013 concerning Functional Positions of Lecturers and the Credit Score, Article 6 verse 5).

Lecturer career development through a functional position is essential in a higher education institution. The human resource management in higher education should be more focused on the potential of lecturers so that they can display their professional profiles based on the three pillars of higher education. For a lecturer's functional promotion to run efficiently, apart from individual efforts, there must also be support from the institution management. Evaluating credit score periodically is crucial as an effort to measure self-efficacy before applying for a promotion to a higher level of lecturer functional position.

A study at a university in Indonesia revealed that promotions and lecturer positions are often delayed due to the factors of the lecturers' motivation and an unsupportive administrative system. Meanwhile, the level and position of a lecturer will affect the quality of teaching and learning and will even affect the accreditation of study programs and institutions. This university has implemented several strategic steps: the formation of an acceleration team for publication, capacity building for human resources, an online archive system, research grants for lecturers who have the potential to professorship level, and the administrative staff's workload distribution especially dealing with promotions and lecturer functional positions (Mahyuni et al., 2020).

Another similar study has also been conducted with the result that the acceleration of lecturer functional positions is performed mainly due to the shortage of lecturer resources with the positions of associate lecturer and professor. This acceleration is performed by increasing the lecturer capacity development in the process of achieving teaching, research, and community service, improving the funding system, developing the filing system, and building a stable evaluation system (Muluk & Amelia, 2019). Moreover, restructuring the lecturer workload, increasing lecturers' motivation to write scientific articles, and developing and structuring information systems for the promotion of lecturer functional positions.

Politeknik Negeri Bandung (Polban) is a vocational high school that focuses on the students' mastery of certain applied skills, with a higher portion of practice than theories. The lecturers' teaching load in Polban is relatively high in one semester with the average teaching hours approximately 30 hours per week. Thus, they do not have sufficient time to do research and community services which eventually becomes an obstacle to accomplishing the three pillars of higher education. This condition causes stagnation in terms of the promotion of functional positions because not all elements of the three pillars of higher education can be completed. As a result, the lecturers are not enthusiastic about conducting the promotion of functional position. Even, there is a condition where they do not propose their functional position promotion for more than 10 years. The condition of lecturers who do not propose the lecturers' functional position in Polban is presented in the following table.

Table 1 The condition of lecturers who do not promote the lecturers' functional position

Level	More than 10 years	Less than 10 years
Instructor	38	45
Assistant Professor	115	51
Associate Professor	77	100
Total	230	196

Table 1 shows that 230 lecturers do not conduct the promotion of their functional position for more than 10 years and 196 lecturers who do not propose their functional promotions in less than 10 years. Based on this condition, it is essential to apply a policy from the management of Polbanto support the acceleration of the promotion of lecturers' functional positions because it will considerably affect the professionalism and quality of lecturers in realizing the institution's vision and missions.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The lecturers' functional position or also known as an academic position is a position that shows the duties, responsibilities, authorities, and rights of a lecturer in a higher education unit which in its implementation is based on certain skills and is independent (Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform No. 17 the Year 2013 concerning the functional position of lecturers and credit score, Article 1 Number 1). The functional position of a lecturer is a position of expertise from the lowest to the highest, consisting of Instructor, Assistant Professor, Associate Professor, and Professors (Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform No. 17 the Year 2013, Article 6). The main duty of the academic position of the lecturer is to conduct education, research, and community service (Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform No. 17 the Year 2013, Article 4).

The determination of the academic position is based on the number of credit scores owned by a lecturer after being assessed by the assessors who are authorized to determine the credit score (Regulation of the Minister of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform No. 17 the Year 2013, Article 6 verse 5). Meanwhile, the formation of functional positions of lecturers is based on a job analysis and workload calculation.

To obtain the functional position, a lecture must fulfill the credit score required for each level of functional position. The fulfillment of the credit score is viewed from each element i.e., education, research, and community service, as well as other supporting elements. However, as stated in Maftuh (2016), the absence of accredited national journals or reputable international journals, as well as the detection of several scientific papers that fall into the category of plagiarism, is a major cause for the promotion of functional positions to Associate Lecturers and Professors is delayed. In addition, the delay was commonly caused by two main factors; the lecturers' motivation and the unsupportive administrative system (Mahyuni et al., 2020), (Dwinanta & Ginting, 2012), (Handayani, 2015).

Coaching and development of lecturers to accomplish the three pillars of higher education that can support them to become professional educators and scientists with the main task of transforming, developing, and disseminating science, technology, and art through the process of education, research, and community service need to be performed by universities (Khayyad, 2019). Therefore, it is recommended that the information system that supports through an application of the Decision Support System is implemented as part of monitoring and evaluation of lecturer performance (Suheri, 2017).

Accelerating the promotion of lecturers' functional positions should be accompanied by improving the input factors and transforming the process of functional position promotion (Muluk & Amelia, 2019). The input factors include capacity building of lecturers in the three pillars of higher education, improvement of the funding system, improvement of the filing system, and a stable evaluation system. Meanwhile, the transformation process includes structuring the lecturers' workload, increasing the motivation for writing scientific papers, and restructuring the Information System that supports the promotion of lecturers' functional position.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research applied the descriptive qualitative method. This method was chosen because the study is used to explore and understand the meaning ascribed to social or humanitarian problems.

The study was conducted in three stages. The first phase is a literature study as a preliminary study. In this phase, some laws and regulations that control the requirements for the promotion of functional positions were collected. Comparative studies to other universities/higher education institutions that have made policies to accelerate the promotion of functional positions were also conducted. The second phase is the questionnaire distribution to lecturers in Polban to evaluate their understanding of the significance of functional position in

their career. The third stage is an analysis of the policy carried out by the management of Polban in supporting the promotion of lecturers' functional positions.

The questionnaire consists of 20 questions, 16 questions are closed questions with 4 answer options, i.e., strongly disagree, disagree, agree, and strongly agree. Then, 4 questions are open questions, meaning that respondents are asked to answer questions based on their understanding and point of view. The questionnaires are used as a guide to conclude each question related to the respondent's knowledge about the obligation to increase the lecturers' functional position as a form of improving professionalism and career. Scoring on each answer to the questionnaire is to conclude the level of understanding based on the following criteria:

Table 2. Criteria Level of Understanding of Risk

Score	Assessment indicators
1	Strongly Disagree
2	Disagree
3	Agree
4	Strongly Agree

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The lecturers' functional position is essentially a government policy in regulating lecturers' careers. Functional positions that consist of Instructor, Assistant Professor, Associate Professor, and Professor are stated in the Regulation of The Minister of Research, Technology, and Higher Education No. 44 the Year 2015 concerning The Standard of National Higher Education and Law No. 12 the Year 2012 about Higher Education. The total credit score should be based on the required credit score for each level, and it is obtained from education and teaching, research, community service, and other supporting elements.

1. Lecturers' Understanding of Functional Position

Technically the instructions for the implementation of functional promotion are regulated in the Circular Letter of The Minister of Education and Culture, Directorate of Higher Education No. 638/E.E4/KP/2020 on the Implementation of Operational Guidelines on the Assessment of Functional Promotion Credit Score. This letter regulates the technical requirements that must be fulfilled by the lecturer to reach a certain level of functional position. In addition, the amount of credit score that must be accumulated to promote the functional position to the next level and the possibility to promote the functional position to the next two levels are also regulated.

Based on this condition, the researchers distributed questionnaires to the lecturers in Polban to evaluate their understanding of the importance of functional promotion in managing their careers. 91 respondents respond the question related to the lecturers' condition in Polban. It is presented in the following figure.

Figure 1 The condition of Lecturers in Polban

The first part of the questionnaire consists of questions related to their understanding and knowledge of the obligation to conduct the functional promotion. The results reveal that 67.70% of respondents know the obligation to conduct the promotion of functional position. A total of 45.20% of respondents confirmed that the information about the requirements and procedures for functional promotion can be accessed easily. Meanwhile, 54.80% of respondents stated that they understand the flow of functional promotion management and 63.70% of respondents agree or understand that each scientific paper to be submitted for functional promotion must be free from plagiarism. Thus, principally, the lecturers in Polban already know and understand the obligations, requirements, and procedures to conduct the functional promotion.

However, this condition is contrary to the number of lecturers who perform functional promotion as described in the previous part. This condition is almost similar to the research conducted by Mahyuni et al., (2020) that the delay of lecturers in the management of functional promotion is influenced by two factors: internal factor (lecturers' motivation) and external factor (less supportive administrative system). In terms of the internal factor, in general, the lecturers know the concerns of their profession and that they must organize their career by conducting the functional promotion.

The following questions are related to the constraints faced by the lecturers in conducting functional promotion. The results show that 62.40% of respondents experienced problems when they propose the functional positions. In addition, 55.90% of respondents stated that the Personnel Department in Polban does not manage the documents required for functional promotion well. In terms of questions related to the scientific paper assessment, 60.20% of respondents agree that the assessors already have a linear field of science with the paper being assessed. For questions related to the process of promotions that were hampered at the credit score assessment stage, as many as 55.90% confirmed that the process of promotions is not hampered at the credit score assessment stage.

The next questions are related to the fulfillment of the Three Pillars of Higher Education elements in one semester. 43% of respondents confirmed that they can meet the credit scores for the element of education and teaching. Then, 54.80% of respondents confirm that they can meet the credit scores for research and community service elements. Based on the responses regarding the fulfillment of the elements of the Three Pillars of Higher Education, reaching certain credit points for elements of education and teaching is not a problem. It is because Polban is a vocational college where the main activity of the lecturers is teaching with the average of teaching credits in one semester is more than 12 credits. From the element of research, 60% of the lecturers' working hours are spent in laboratories, so the research carried out by Polban lecturers mostly comes from the results of practicum in the laboratory. The element of community service also is not a problem because every year there are approximately 50 proposals for community service that are accepted and funded by Polban. If each proposal is submitted by five lecturers, it means that as many as 250 lecturers carry out community service activities. Apart from community service, which is funded by Polban, some lecturers also conduct community service independently and self-financing.

The last questions are related to the support from Polban management in the process of functional position promotion. The results show that 45.20% of respondents stated that they do not get support from both Polban management and colleagues for the functional promotion. In addition, as many as 50.50% of respondents confirmed that they never get support from their superiors directly. Concerning the questions related to the work atmosphere, 65.60% of respondents responded that the work atmosphere in Polban does not support the process of accelerating the functional promotion process. Based on the results above, the support from management, direct superiors, colleagues, and even the work atmosphere has not been fully established in the process of functional promotion. Motivation in the form of support is necessary for the lecturers, considering the role of lecturers is very central and strategic so coaching and development through management support in the process of functional promotion are essential (Khayyad, 2019).

2. Management Policy in Supporting the Lecturers' Functional Position Promotion

The factors that affect the implementation of accelerating functional position promotions are presented in the following figure.

Figure 2. Variables that affect the implementation of functional position promotions

The figure shows that the process of functional promotion is influenced by several factors: the lecturers' knowledge of the functional positions, socialization of functional positions, procedure of application submission, and support from the management.

To facilitate the lecturers in conducting credit score assessments, currently Polban has provided a system called Credit Score Assessment Information System that can be used by the lecturers in submitting their scientific paper assessments and functional promotions online through the website <https://sipak.polban.ac.id> since March 2021. Through this system, Polban management has a target to shorten the duration starting from the assessment of scientific papers to the decision of the Senate regarding the approval of lecturers' functional promotions. For the assessment of scientific papers, Polban management has a maximum target of 40 working days for a reviewer to assess one paper. Before the existence of this system, a reviewer sometimes spent months to assess a scientific paper so that the process of functional promotion was hampered. Moreover, the assessor team must have a field of science that is linear with the field of scientific papers being assessed so that the assessment can be more objective and is expected to help lecturers in obtaining the maximum credit score.

In addition to shortening the duration of the assessment of scientific papers, this system also helps to administer the documents needed for the assessment of scientific papers or the promotions of functional positions online, so that there are no longer found conditions of missing or scattered application documents that can hamper the process of promotion. With this website, it is hoped that it will facilitate the process of promotion, although technically the website is still being developed. However, currently, there have been an action from the Polban management to support lecturers in conducting the promotion of functional positions.

The development of an information system/website is a new paradigm in human resource management in the New Public Management Perspective (Syafri&Alwi, 2014). Changes in environmental factors such as economic, technological, social, and political changes affect human resource management in achieving the effectiveness and efficiency of public organizations. Polban management in this case must be responsive to those changes, especially advances in information and technology so that it can facilitate lecturers to apply for the promotion of functional positions online.

Another support carried out by the management of Polban is to encourage and motivate Polban lecturers to apply for functional promotion, especially for the ones who have not conducted the promotion of functional positions for more than 10 years. Polban management in this case the Deputy Director of Academic Affairs issued a circular letter containing the obligation to immediately conduct the promotion of functional positions that are mapped according to the level and number of credit scores required.

The promotion of functional position consists of regular promotion (promotion to the next level of functional position) and non-regular promotion (promotion to the next-two levels of functional position) as stated in the Circular Letter of The Ministry of Education and Culture Directorate of Higher Education No.

638/E. E4/KP/2020 concerning the implementation of operational guidelines on the assessment of functional promotion and credit scores. The scheme of regular promotion is presented as follows:

Figure 2. The scheme of regular promotion

To conduct regular promotion, a lecturer must fulfill the specified requirements or the number of credit scores that have been set for each level. Meanwhile, the scheme of non-regular promotion is presented as follows:

Figure 3. The scheme of non-regular promotion

The non-regular promotion can only be conducted once by lecturers with a doctoral degree. For example, an assistant professor with a credit score of 200 can conduct a promotion to an associate professor or a professor with a credit score of 850 can conduct a promotion to a professor level with a credit score of 1050.

In terms of the regulation, the existence of a non-regular promotion scheme and online functional promotion facilities have enabled the lecturers to conduct the promotion of functional positions so that the acceleration program for lecturers' functional promotions at Polban can run effectively. This can be seen from the distribution of the functional positions of the lecturers in Polban and their levels as shown in the following table:

Table 3 Distribution of Functional Positions of Polban Lecturers

Rank and Class	Functional Position	Number
III a	No functional position	3
	Instructor	26
	Assistant Professor	4
III/b	No functional position	85
	Lecturer Assistants	62
	Assistant Professor	5
III/ c	Assistant Professor	135
	Associate Professor	1
III/d	Assistant Professor	32
	Associate Professor	2
IV/a	Associate Professor	137
	Professor	1
IV/ b	Associate Professor	39
	Professor	1
IV/c	Associate Professor	7
	Professor	1
IV/d	Professor	1

Based on this distribution, most of the lecturers in Polban are at level III/c, Assistant Professor, and IV/a Associate Professor. The functional positions of Professors are still very limited. With the support from Polban Management and the ease of procedures in conducting the promotion of functional positions, it is hoped that it will be a motivation for the lecturers to start managing their careers.

V. CONCLUSION

Lecturers at Polban already have a good understanding of the obligation to conduct the promotion of functional position and knowledge of the requirements and procedures for the promotion. However, there are still lecturers who have obstacles in terms of administering documents that are not well organized. Another obstacle is that the management, direct superiors, colleagues, and the work atmosphere at Polban have not fully supported lecturers in conducting functional promotions. To reduce obstacles and increase the number of lecturers who conduct promotions, currently, Polban management has begun to provide support to lecturers in the form of the Credit Score Assessment Information System or Sistem Informasi Penilaian Angka Kredit (SIPAK) which facilitate the lecturers to evaluate scientific papers and propose the functional promotions online.

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